

ABSTRACT

Viral Metatranscriptomics and Machine-Learning at the Vertical Transmission Interface of Chiroptera Circulating in Northeastern Brazil

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RNA viruses have been responsible for causing severe epidemics and pandemics all across the world in recent decades. This scenario has been constantly studied by viral epidemiological surveillance and molecular evolution methodologies to investigate the appearance of new viral agents in order to respond to these new threats before they reach the human population. In this context, bats have received notable attention for harboring several viral pathogens of zoonotic importance, such as Rabies, Ebola, Marburg, Nipah, SARS-CoV, MERS-CoV, SARS-CoV-2 pandemic, among others. Given this, the present project will apply techniques involving metatranscriptomics, Bayesian inference and machine-learning to investigate the presence, characterize, identify genetic signatures and map the diversity of RNA viruses at the interface of vertical transmission of different bats species inhabiting Brazilian Northeast. Through our approach, we also aim to test the hypothesis of vertical transmission of different viral agents through intra-host gene expression patterns, in addition to studying their evolution through phylodynamics, phylogeographic and phyloanatomy methods, approaches not undertaken in earlier investigations. We hope that such contributions will help to clarify mechanisms behind viral intra-host evolutionary dynamics and spread over time, as well as will promote measures on behalf of Public Health strategies aimed at preventing future epidemics and pandemics episodes.

Keywords: Bats; Viral Evolution; Machine Learning; Metatranscriptomics.

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